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A NKG7 and NKG2D (KLRK1) co-regulated network.

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We describe here co-regulation of genes important for CD8 T-cell cytotoxic function by NKG2D (KLRK1) and NKG7 including the CD8A receptor, co-stimulatory molecule CD2, T-cell co-receptor molecule CD3D, the granzymes GZMA, GZMH, and GZMK, nuclear effectors of T-cell fate and exhaustion EOMES and THEMIS, NK cell genes CD247 and KLRD1, CCL5 and the pattern recognition receptor PYHIN.